

European Conference on Information Literacy 2017

Information Needs, Information behaviour, and Scholarly Information Literacy amongst PhD Students: An Interview-Based Study

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Interview Guide

Demographic questions

1. Tell me about yourself: Where did you grow up? What were your experiences with libraries as a young adult?
2. Tell me about your academic background: Where did you do your B.Sc. degree and what was your major/focus? Where did you earn your M.Sc. degree?
3. Tell me about your work at Chalmers: When did you start your PhD? Which department do you belong to? Briefly describe your research, and your expertise. Are you a research assistant? Do you teach?

Library use

1. Tell me how you use information resources: Which resources (databases, journals, etc.) do you use? And how often? Can you tell me about issues you have encountered, technical or of other kind (linking, full-text etc.)?
2. Tell me about the library website: How often do you use it? Can you tell me how you use it and if you have encountered any problems when accessing the site? Are you aware of the services that the library provides?

How do you review the literature?

1. Tell me how you scope and map the literature: When you first started your PhD? And later in your degree program (if applicable)? Have you encounter any problems and/or difficulties?
2. Tell me about the standard you need to follow for reviewing the literature in your field: Are you aware of what is expected from the journals you will publish in?

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Publishing

1. Tell me about the publishing process: Have you experienced the publishing process as author and/or peer reviewer?
2. Tell me about journal choices: How do you and/or your colleagues select journals to follow/publish in?
3. Tell me about conference and conference proceedings: How do you and/or your colleagues choose conferences to follow? Do you read conference proceedings?

Open Science

1. Tell me about open software: What is your opinion and/or experience regarding the reuse of open software programs?
2. Tell me about open data: What is your opinion and/or experience regarding the storage and reuse of research data?

Stay up to date

1. In which ways do you monitor the latest developments in your field?
2. What do you and/or your colleagues regard as a challenge in this area?

Patent

1. What about patents? Would they be useful to you and/or your colleagues? In which way/s?

